

Synthesis, characterization and electrical conductivity of some bivalent metal complexes of ONS donor ligand

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Abstract : The solid complexes of VO^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with a new tridentate ligand 3-*{(1E)-N-(benzylthio)carbonothioyl}ethanehydrazonoyl*-4-hydroxybenzoic acid derived from 5-carboxy-2-hydroxyacetophenone and *S*-benzylidithiocarbazate, have been synthesized and characterized by analytical, magnetic susceptibility measurements, molecular weight determination, IR and electronic spectra and thermal analysis. From the analytical and thermal data the stoichiometry of the complexes has been found to be 1 : 1. (metal : ligand). The molar conductivity data show them to be non-electrolytes. IR spectral data suggest that the ligand behaves as a dibasic tridentate with ONS donor sequence towards metal ions. TGA showed the presence of coordinated water molecules in all chelates except VO^{IV} and Cu^{II}. The solid state electrical conductivity of the complexes are found to be low with σ in the range of 10^{-11} – 10^{-7} Ω^{-1} cm⁻¹, however the conductivities of all complexes increases as the temperature increases from 313 to 403 K, indicating their semiconducting behaviour. The electrical activation energies of the complexes, which were in the range 0.260 to 0.712 eV, were calculated from Arrhenius plots.

Keywords : Bivalent metal ions, ONS donors, conductivity.

Transition metal complexes of Schiff bases have been amongst the most widely studied coordination compounds in the past few years, since they are found to be of importance as biochemical, analytical and antimicrobial reagents¹⁻³. Schiff bases containing polyfunctional groups offer many practical advantages and unique structural environment for complexation⁴. Thiosemicarbazone derivatives have a great importance in chemistry and biology due to their antiprotozoal, antibacterial, antiviral and antineoplastic activities⁵. Various workers have discussed metal complex of thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones⁶⁻⁸. In view of above importance of thiosemicarbazones and its derivatives, it was thought worthwhile to prepare the metal complexes of VO^{IV}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} with Schiff base 3-*{(1E)-N-[(benzylthio)carbonothioyl]ethanehydrazonoyl}*-4-hydroxybenzoic acid derived from 5-carboxy-2-hydroxyacetophenone and *S*-benzylidithiocarbazate. The complexes being reported have been characterized by various physico-chemical methods.

Results and discussion

Analytical data for the complexes indicate 1 : 1 stoichiometry for all the complexes. All the complexes de-

composes at high temperature (305-330 °C) and are stable in air and are partially or insoluble in common organic solvents and soluble in DMF and DMSO. The molar conductance of the complexes falls in range of 8.50–19.50 ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in DMF (10⁻³ M) solution indicating their non-electrolytic behaviour⁹. Such a non-zero molar conductance value for each of the complex in the present study is most probably due to the strong donor capacity of dimethylformamide, which may lead to the displacement of anionic ligand and change of electrolyte type¹⁰.

The condensation of 5-carboxy-2-hydroxyacetophenone with *S*-benzylidithiocarbazate in ethanolic medium yields the Schiff base. The formation of this Schiff base is further confirmed by its IR and ¹H NMR data. Its ¹H NMR spectrum shows signals at δ 14.7 (1H, s, Ar-COOH), 12.69 (1H, s, phenolic OH), 11.30 (1H, s, imino), 7.46, 7.30 and 7.16 (3H, m, phenyl), 2.46 (3H, s, methyl) and 4.47 ppm (SCH₂) respectively¹¹. The presence of -NH proton resonance and the absence of -SH proton resonance further support the thione nature of ligand¹⁰.

The IR spectrum of Schiff base exhibits a strong band at 1030 cm⁻¹ due to ν (C=S) stretch, which indicates the thione nature of the ligand. This is further supported by the presence of a band in the region 3095–3230 cm⁻¹ due

to the $\nu(\text{NH})$ band of the hydrazide residue. The disappearance of bands due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{NH})$ in the spectra of complexes supports the thioenolization of the $>\text{C}=\text{S}$ group and coordination of the sulphur to the metal¹². A broad band around 3400 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $\nu(\text{OH})$ (phenolic) band and the absence of this band in the complexes suggests the coordination of the *ortho* phenolic oxygen atom. This is further supported by the shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic) band from 1260 of the Schiff base to $1290\text{--}1310\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (azomethine) band of the ligand appears at 1622 cm^{-1} and this band is shifted to lower frequency by $16\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating coordination through the azomethine nitrogen atom. In the far infrared spectra of the complexes, the bands observed in the region $540\text{--}480$, $475\text{--}450$ and $390\text{--}410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are may be due to M-O, M-N and M-S modes respectively. In the case of oxovanadium complex a band observed at 960 cm^{-1} is due to $\text{V}=\text{O}$ mode¹³. The presence of coordinated water in all complexes except copper and oxovanadium is shown by the appearance of a broad bands in the region $3400\text{--}3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by another additional bands at $835\text{--}845\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations respectively.

The VO^{IV} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes at room temperature exhibit magnetic moment 1.42 , 5.85 , 5.41 , 4.72 , 2.93 and 1.33 B.M. , respectively, in accordance with the spin only value indicating their high-spin nature. Low value of magnetic moment for VO^{IV} and Cu^{II} complexes is may be due to the presence of weak magnetic interactions between two metal centers in the complexes.

The electronic spectrum of Mn^{II} complex exhibits weak absorption bands at 17200 , 23809 and 27030 cm^{-1} due to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, transitions, respectively in an octahedral coordination around metal ion¹⁴. The extremely weak intensities of these bands are indicative of their doubly forbidden nature. The iron(II) complex exhibits absorption bands at 19410 and 19300 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to octahedral geometry. The first band may be due to the ${}^5T_{2g}(D) \rightarrow {}^5E_g$ transition, while other band may be charge transfer in origin. The crystal field parameters have been calculated and values are : $Dq = 1041\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 540\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $C = 2160\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.51$ and $\beta^{\circ} = 49.05\%$ respectively. The Co^{II} complex shows two bands at 8940 and 18185 cm^{-1} due to the transitions, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\nu_1)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$, respectively with the following electronic spectral parameters $Dq = 1005\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 710\text{ cm}^{-1}$, β

$= 0.731$ and $\beta^{\circ} = 26.87\%$ respectively. The position of the spectral bands and the electronic parameters of the complex identifies the complex possess an octahedral structure with strong covalence¹⁵. The electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex shows three bands at 9660 , 16080 and 23831 cm^{-1} due to the ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively. The $\nu_2 : \nu_1$ ratio occurs in the usual range ($1.6\text{--}1.82$) and identified the complex to possess an octahedral structure¹⁶. The electronic spectral parameters for Ni^{II} complex were calculated and values are $Dq = 966\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 71.2\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.66$ and $\text{IJFSE} = 132.14\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The presence of strong covalence is indicated from the reduction of the Racah parameter B from the free ion value 1056 cm^{-1} and from the β° of 34% . The electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex show broad band at 15385 cm^{-1} due to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transition in a square planar geometry. The electronic spectrum of VO^{IV} complex shows weak bands at 12320 , 14530 and 181.60 cm^{-1} which are assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$, transitions, respectively. These transitions are in accordance with square pyramidal geometry¹⁷. Although molecular weight measurements on Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and VO^{IV} complexes were not possible due to their insolubility in suitable organic solvents, such measurement on Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes indicated their dimeric nature. (Found 856 , 403 calculated 896 and 420) The electronic spectra of Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complex were not well resolved and do not show any d-d transitions. But their μ_{eff} value suggests their diamagnetic nature as expected.

Thermal analyses of the complexes were carried out in dynamic air atmosphere. The Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes show weight loss 9.18 and 10.08% (calcd. 8.40 and 8.54%) respectively at $\sim 1.80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ which corresponds to loss of two coordinated water molecules per metal (Fig. 1.). The Fe^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes show mass loss 13.52 and $1.2.52\%$ respectively, in the temperature range $180\text{--}200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ corresponding to three water molecules, while Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes show loss of one coordinated water molecule (4.73 and 4.11%). In TGA studies the VO^{IV} and Cu^{II} complexes decompose in one step beyond $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, suggesting the absence of any water molecules in these complexes. The second step of thermo grams shows continuous weight loss due to oxidative decomposition of the ligand leading to the formation of respective oxides and agrees with analytical data for the metal contents. The thermal data have been analyzed by Coats-Redfern equation for the kinetic parameters of decomposition and values are given in Table 1. The values of

Fig. 1. Thermograms of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes : (A) Co^{II} , (B) Ni^{II} , (C) Zn^{II} .

kinetic parameters show only slight variation, which is quite apparent from their structure difference. The negative values for energy of activation indicate that the activated complex has a more ordered structure than the reactants and the reactions are slower than normal¹⁸. This is further support by low value of frequency factor. The thermal stability follows the order, $\text{Co} > \text{Mn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu} > \text{VO} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd}$.

The DC conductivity measurements of the complexes were made over a wide range of temperature 313-403 K in their compressed pellet form. The electrical conductivity (σ) varies exponentially with absolute temperature according to the relation $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp -E_a/RT$, where E_a is the activation energy of the semiconductor and σ_0 is a constant. The plots of $\ln \sigma$ vs $1/T$ are almost linear. The conductivity increases with increase in temperature and decrease upon cooling over the above temperature range and their values lies in the range 10^{-11} to $10^{-7} (\Omega \text{ cm})^{-1}$. The electrical conductivity at room temperature is in the

order $\text{VO} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cd} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cu} > \text{Mn} > \text{Fe} > \text{H}_2\text{L}$. and the activation energy increases in the order $\text{Cd} > \text{Fe} > \text{Ni} > \text{VO} > \text{Zn} > \text{H}_2\text{L} > \text{Mn} > \text{Co} > \text{Cu}$. The results indicate that the electrical conductivity of metal complexes is slightly higher than that of the ligand, which may be due to the incorporation of metal ion in the ligand increase the ionization tendency¹⁹.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. *S*-Benzyldithiocarbamate was prepared by known method¹¹ while 5-carboxy2-hydroxyacetophenone was prepared by Friedal Craft reaction.

Elemental analyses were carried out with a Carlo Erba 11.08 analyzer at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. ¹H NMR spectrum of ligand was obtained with a JEOL PMX 60 SI spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1600 spectrophotometer as KBr disc. Diffuse reflectance

Table 1. Thermal and electrical conductivity data of complexes

Compd.	Electrical conductivity ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	Activation energy (eV)	D_H ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Thermal activation energy	Z (s^{-1})	$-\Delta S$ ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
[H ₂ L]	3.83×10^{-11} 2.50×10^{-10}	0.455	173	22.15	317.46	173.62
[Mn.L.2H ₂ O] ₂	5.72×10^{-11} 2.64×10^{-9}	0.446	315	96.54	183.05	198.00
[Fe.L.3H ₂ O]	1.58×10^{-11} 6.00×10^{-9}	0.695	312	65.45	219.64	214.04
[Co.L.2H ₂ O]	8.20×10^{-10} 6.61×10^{-8}	0.307	305	69.43	193.04	210.10
[Ni.L3H ₂ O]	5.72×10^{-10} 4.25×10^{-8}	0.643	315	32.45	264.00	220.00
[Cu.L] ₂	1.53×10^{-10} 6.20×10^{-7}	0.260	325	58.94	210.00	209.38
[VOL] ₂	2.50×10^{-9} 1.42×10^{-7}	0.599	310	30.26	244.00	238.00
[Zn.L.H ₂ O]	1.92×10^{-10} 8.20×10^{-7}	0.585	330	33.61	249.50	210.50
[Cd.L.H ₂ O]	2.85×10^{-10} 1.75×10^{-7}	0.712	317	24.27	304.47	205.49

H = Half decomposition temperature.

spectra were done on a Cary 2300 spectrophotometer at IIT, Chennai. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed on a Ciouy balance at room temperature using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as cali brant. Molecular weights were determined by Rast's camphor method. TG analysis of the complexes was carried out on a manually operated thermobalance setup in our laboratory and instrument was calibrated with crystalline copper sulphate. Metal contents were determined by volumetrically and gravimetrically after decomposing the complex with conc. HCl and HNO₃ and igniting the oxides₂₀. Solid-state electrical conductivity of compounds was measured by conventional two-probe method over 313-403 K temperature range.

Preparation of Schiff base : A hot methanolic solution (Ca. 15 cm³) of 5-carboxy-2-hydroxy acetophenone (1 mmol) was added to a hot solution of *S*-benzylidithiocarbazate (1 mmol) in 15 cm³ of methanol and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h on a water bath. After reducing the solvent to Ca. 10 cm³, the solution was cooled to room temperature and kept over night. The separated solid was filtered, washed with methanol dried at ambient temperature and finally recrystallized from hot methanol. Yield 70%; m.p. 173 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Anal.

Found : C, 56.40; H, 4.25; N, 8.16; S, 18.39. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₃S₂ : C, 56.63; H, 4.41; N, 7.71; S, 17.27%.

Synthesis of complex : To a hot solution of ligand (1 mmol) in methanol (40 cm³) Co(CH₃COO)₂.4H₂O was added with vigorous shaking. The resulting solution was refluxed on a water bath for 4-5 h. After reducing the volume of the solution to Ca. 15 cm³, it was cooled to room temperature. The separated solid was filtered, washed with methanol, diethyl ether and dried in air at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Other complexes were prepared following the above method, or with slight variation thereof, in 70-80% yield.

Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₅S₂Mn : Mn, 12.23; C, 45.44; H, 4.00; N, 6.23; S, 14.23%; Found : Mn, 12.92; C, 44.72; H, 3.96; N, 6.03; S, 14.82%. Calcd. for C₁₇H₂₀N₂O₆S₂Fe : Fe, 11.93; C, 43.63; H, 4.27; N, 5.98; S, 13.68%; Found : Fe, 11.95; C, 43.25; H, 4.00; N, 6.21; S, 4.25%. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₅S₂Co : Co, 13.08; C, 45.04; H, 3.97; N, 6.18; S, 14.13%; Found : Co, 12.96; C, 44.75; H, 4.03; N, 6.15; S, 14.85%. Calcd. for C₁₇H₂₀N₂O₆S₂Ni : Ni, 12.46; C, 43.34; H, 4.24; N, 5.94; S, 13.59%; Found : Ni, 12.69; C, 42.16; H, 4.12; N, 6.03; S, 13.95%. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₄N₂O₃S₂Cu : Cu,

15.12; C, 48.58; H, 3.36; N, 13.33; S, 16.33%; Found, Cu, 15.68; C, 48.21; H, 3.03; N, 7.00; S, 16.15%. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_4S_2V$: V, 12.04; C, 48.11; H, 3.30; N, 6.60; S, 16.15%; Found : V, 11.69; C, 47.58; H, 3.15; N, 6.83; S, 15.85%. Calcd for $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_4S_2Zn$: Zn, 14.82; C, 46.25; H, 3.62; N, 6.34; S, 14.52%; Found : Zn, 14.38; C, 46.21; H, 3.52; N, 6.18; S, 14.89%. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_4S_2Cd$: Cd, 22.95; C, 41.83; H, 3.27; N, 5.92; S, 13.11%; Found : Cd, 22.83; C, 40.86; H, 3.10; N, 5.92; S, 12.87%.

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